

Appendix

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

TABLE I depicts the list of questions we used to collect data from the survey respondents. The questions were designed into four types: single-nominal response (SNR), multi-nominal response (MNR), Likert-scaled response (LSR), and open-ended response (OER).

TABLE I
QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

ID	Question/statement	Responses	Type
<i>A. Respondent profile</i>			
Q01	Gender	Male Female	SNR
Q02	Age group	≤ 30 years 31 – 40 years 41 – 50 years > 50 years	SNR
Q03	Background education	Doctoral (PhD) Master	SNR
Q04	Experience as faculty	< 1 year 1 – 5 years 6 – 10 years > 10 years	SNR
<i>B. Generative AI usage</i>			
Q05	I have used the following GenAI tools	ChatGPT Grammarly Jenni AI Microsoft Copilot Perplexity GitHub Copilot IntelliCode Codex ChatPDF Google Gemini Typeset.io Never use any GenAI tools Others (please specify) ...	MNR
Q06	How confident are you in using GenAI tools?	0: not at all 1: somewhat confident 2: moderately confident 3: confident 4: highly confident	LSR
Q07	How frequently do you use GenAI tools to support your... (a) teaching activities? (b) research activities? (c) community service activities?	0: never 1: rarely 2: occasionally 3: frequently 4: always	LSR
Q08	To what extent do you agree that GenAI tools effectively support your... (a) teaching activities (b) research activities (c) community service activities	0: strongly disagree 1: disagree 2: neutral 3: agree 4: strongly agree	LSR
Q09	Describe how you use GenAI tools to support your... (a) teaching activities (b) research activities (c) community service activities	Open text	OER

ID	Question/statement	Responses	Type
<i>C. Opportunity and Concerns</i>			
Q10	GenAI tools have the potential to promote ...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Encouraging innovation in learning models, such as flipped learning, hybrid learning, etc. (b) Improving learning quality by creating richer and more in-depth learning materials (c) Optimizing lecturers' time and resources (d) Strengthening lifelong learning skills (e) Promoting equal access to education 	MNR
Q11	The most concerning impact or risk of using GenAI tools is ...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Risk of becoming too dependent on AI tools for learning (b) There is a risk of cheating and breaches of academic ethics and integrity (c) Risk of inaccurate, hallucinated, or misleading responses (d) Risk of privacy breaches and misuse of personal data (e) Risk of cyberattacks (f) These risks are manageable and no need to worry 	SNR